

Investigation of the dust load and metal content and their impacts from the Saldanha Bay area

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1. Introduction

1.1 Dust emission, air pollution, and impacts

Air pollution is widely recognised as one of the greatest environmental threats to human health [1]. It ranks as the fourth most deadly risk factor globally, after tobacco use, unhealthy diets, and high blood pressure [1–3]. Each year, air pollution contributes to approximately 6.7 million premature deaths worldwide [1,4,5]. Given its serious health impacts, it is crucial to understand both the sources and effects of air pollution to develop effective strategies to reduce and prevent it.

Air pollution is caused by gases and/or fine particles. These fine inhalable particles, also referred to as either dust, aerosol, or particulate matter (PM), pose the greatest risk to human health [4,6,7]¹. Dust particles that are suspended in the air are commonly categorised based on their size: particles smaller than 10 micrometres in diameter (PM₁₀), particles smaller than 2.5 micrometres (PM_{2.5}), and particles smaller than 1 micrometre (PM₁). Smaller particles, such as PM_{2.5}, can penetrate deeper into the respiratory system when inhaled, making them more harmful than larger particles. In addition to size, the concentration of particles in the air and the harmful substances they carry are important factors. For instance, dust may carry potentially toxic metals or pathogens that increase health risks (Figure 1). Such potentially toxic metals include chromium (Cr), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), and lead (Pb). It is furthermore important to consider the concentration of these metals in the dust since higher concentrations are generally more harmful [8–11].

Dust particles in the atmosphere originate from both natural and anthropogenic (human-made) sources. Natural sources are often associated with semi-arid and arid regions and include rivers and lakes that occasionally dry up (also called ephemeral rivers), dunes, volcanic activity, pollen and micro-organisms. Anthropogenic sources include agriculture, mining, industrial processes, fires, and vehicle exhaust. Over the past century, emissions from anthropogenic sources have increased significantly due to industrial expansion, urban development, and changes in land use [12–17]. Climate change can also alter emissions from natural environments due to changes in surface moisture and vegetation, among others [18–20]. The presence of potentially toxic metals has especially been associated with anthropogenic dust sources, such as road dust, mining and industry [21–25].

Besides the impact on human health, dust particles can influence the environment (Figure 1). One of the most prominent depositional areas of dust is the ocean and large water bodies like rivers, where the particles can play a key role in biogeochemical cycles and ecosystem health [26–28]. Dust can provide important nutrients to the ocean, and these nutrients act like fertilisers that sustain the organisms, such as phytoplankton, in the ocean. Dust can even trigger short phytoplankton blooms in nutrient-limited regions [29,30]. Since phytoplankton are the base of the ocean's food web, dust particles that provide nutrients can play key roles in the ocean's ecosystems. Increases in anthropogenic dust may increase the bioavailability of nutrients like phosphorus [31,32] and iron (Fe) [33,34] but can also deliver high metal loads that may become toxic to marine organisms [35]. The effects of dust depend on the particle load and

¹ For this report, the term "dust" will be used to describe any type of particulate matter or particles in the air

Figure 1. A schematic overview depicts the emission of industrial dust particles, their potential content and their transport to residential areas where they could impact public health. Furthermore, the particle deposition impacts the oceans' biogeochemistry.

composition, local marine conditions, and existing microbial and phytoplankton communities [36,37]. Here, potential anthropogenic or natural dust sources that are in proximity to the marine system would be particularly relevant. Despite its importance, little is known about how anthropogenic activities influence dust emissions and transport from southern Africa to adjacent marine systems.

1.2 Saldanha Bay

Dust emission is a significant concern in the vicinity of Saldanha Bay, located in the Western Cape Province on the west coast of South Africa (Figure 2). The port of Saldanha Bay functions as an important industrial hub responsible for processing and exporting large volumes of mining materials, particularly iron ore and manganese ore sourced from the Northern Cape Province. Beyond ore processing, the nearby Besaansklip industrial area hosts facilities that produce metals such as Pb, Cu, and Zn, as well as steel products, including galvanised steel, for export. Industrial operations in this region have steadily expanded since the early 2000s [38]. Future plans for the expansion of the industrial area include the expansion of the processing capacities and the development of green hydrogen facilities.

Figure 2. The Saldanha Bay Municipality is delineated in dotted lines. Also indicated are the port area and industrial area, the main towns and the West Coast National Park.

The ongoing and planned industrial developments contribute to emissions of dust, which are often visible when deposited as a thin, red layer in the surrounding environment (Figure 3). The transportation, storage, and processing of iron ore are likely additional sources of the visible dust emission in the area. However, the other industrial activities, including the transport of ores, mining materials, and metals, and the processing of these materials, likely add to the particle emissions. Saldanha Bay Municipality contains residential areas

and important national protected areas (Figure 2). The Saldanha Bay Municipality is home to approximately 123,000 people, many of whom could be exposed to the emitted dust. The emission of dust in this region has raised concerns about its impact on public health, particularly for residents living near the port. The prominent southern wind in the area can transport the dust particles over the Municipality [39]. Furthermore, the impact on the environment, such as the adjacent marine areas, should be considered.

Figure 3. The iron ore port in Saldanha Bay showing the red dust deposits.

2. This research

2.1 Aims and objectives

The general aim of the project was to “Investigate the dust load and metal content from an industrial hub (greater Saldanha Bay area and beyond, Western Cape)” and create a report to be shared with the Municipality of Saldanha Bay & Air Quality Management in the Western Cape Government. This work is a continuation of the BIOGRIP project that was started in 2023 and which is reported in Vos et al. [40]. These efforts are summarised in section 2.2. This project also investigated the potential impact of dust on human health and the potential impact of dust on the oceans' biogeochemistry. Therefore, in summary, the three aims are:

1. Determine the dust load and metal content
2. Determine the potential health risks
3. Determine the potential ocean impact

To determine associated metal content and potential health impact, we focused on investigating the presence of Al, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Sr, Mo, Cd, Sn, Sb, Ba, and Pb (summarised in Table 1). These metals were selected since they are associated with anthropogenic particulate emissions, which could have a negative impact on human health and the environment [41]. To achieve this, several approaches for monitoring, sampling, and analysing dust are used.

Table 1. Potentially toxic metals that are examined in this report due to their association with anthropogenic dust and documented adverse effects on human health.

Abbreviation	Full name
Al	Aluminium
V	Vanadium
Cr	Chromium
Mn	Manganese
Fe	Iron
Co	Cobalt
Ni	Nickel
Cu	Copper
Zn	Zinc
As	Arsenic
Se	Selenium
Sr	Strontium
Mo	Molybdenum
Cd	Cadmium
Sn	Tin
Sb	Antimony
Ba	Barium
Pb	Lead

To guide the aims, six main approaches are used (Figure 4): PM monitoring, passive sampling, active sampling, soil and wipe sampling, microbial measurements, and ocean impact experiments. How the aims and methodologies relate to each

other is discussed in sections 2.1.1 to 2.1.3. Furthermore, the spatial and temporal extent, as well as the data gathered from the different methodologies, are illustrated in Figure 5, and details are presented in section 3.

Figure 4. Schematic overview of dust impacts and the key approaches used to investigate them: PM monitoring, microbial measurements, passive and active sampling, and ocean impact experiments. The main aims are presented in sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2. and the associated methods in section 3.

	PM monitoring	Passive sampling	Active sampling	Soil and wipe sampling	Microbial measurements	Ocean impact experiments
Spatial	Two locations, Vredenburg and IDZ	Up to six locations, see table x	One location, the IDZ	High spatial distribution	Four locations	Not relevant
Temporal	2-minute interval measurements, from 2023 onwards	2-monthly interval, from 2023 onwards	Daily interval, from 14/4/25 to 21/4/25	Sing point measurement, on 14/4/25 to 21/4/25	Two 6-hour measurements	Not relevant
Data collected	PM _{2.5} concentration in the air (ng m ⁻³)	Metal concentration in the bulk dust (in ppm or mg/kg) and provides dust for ocean impact experiments	Metal concentration in the air (mg m ⁻³), the metal concentration of particle size fraction, and the solubility of metals.	Metal concentration in the soil (in ppm or mg/kg) and deposited on surface (in mg/cm ² and in ppm or mg/kg)	The microbial communities in the air and the metal concentrations in the air associated with these communities	The response of phytoplankton communities from the coast and the response to dust from this region

Figure 5. A schematic overview of the main methodologies employed, their spatial and temporal resolution, and the key data generated by each method. These methods are presented in more detail in section 3.

2.1.1 Dust load and metal content

A range of sampling approaches was applied to investigate dust load and metal concentrations across multiple time scales, particle size fractions, and media (atmospheric and terrestrial). Combining these different approaches facilitates the broadening of our understanding of air quality and its impact on the environment. Our key tasks here were:

- Determine the particle concentration suspended in the air
- Determine the airborne metal concentration
- Determine the concentration of metals in deposited particles in the soil and on public benches

Each of these tasks uses multiple methodologies, which are described below.

The load of the fine suspended particles (i.e., the PM_{2.5} concentration in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) is measured at high frequency (between 1- and 2-minute intervals) using an array of PM_{2.5} sensors². The high temporal resolution of these methods is a major advantage, but the initial monitoring phase involved only two sensors, resulting in limited spatial coverage. To increase spatial coverage, low-cost sensors were developed at Stellenbosch University and tested for validation and calibration in collaboration with municipal monitoring stations. These new low-cost sensors allow measurements at more locations around Saldanha Bay. The data collected by these sensors, and the development of new sensors are described in more detail in section 3.1.

To determine the metal content, both the concentration of the metals in the ambient air in cubic meters of air (in mg m^{-3} or $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and the concentration of metals in the particles (in mg kg^{-1}) are considered. These datasets of metal concentrations (expressed per unit air or per particle) are generated using two different sampling approaches: *active sampling*, which allows for the measurement of the concentration of metal in the air, and *passive sampling*, which allows for the measurement of metal concentration in the particles. Here, active sampling relies on the active intake of air using a pump mechanism to filter particles from the air, whereas passive sampling relies on the gathering of dust particles without such mechanisms, mainly relying on gravimetric deposition of dust. Although passive samplers do not provide metal concentrations per unit air, their low cost and minimal maintenance requirements make them well-suited for long-term measurements across multiple locations. The details of the passive sampling methodology are described in section 3.2. In contrast, active sampling is a relatively expensive and labour-intensive method, resulting in lower resolution data. Active sampling does allow for the sampling of dust associated with specific air volumes, thus providing the dust concentration of the air (in mg m^{-3}). Analyses of this dust can give insight into the metal concentration in the air (in mg m^{-3}), and active sampling can also allow size fractionated samples. The details of the active sampling methodology are summarised in section 3.3.

Lastly, the metal content in dust on public benches and in the soil was analysed. This sampling would not cover a temporal space but would allow a high spatial resolution. The results of these methodologies can also provide preliminary insight into the risks

² Often the term sensing device is used for these instruments. The term sensors and sensing devices are used interchangeably throughout this document

associated with people's exposure to this dust and potential impacts on the ecology. Furthermore, the dust from public benches was sampled using so-called ghost wipes, which provide further insight into the dust that the public is exposed to and the spatial variance of this dust.

2.1.2 Potential health risk

To address the potential health risk of the dust in Saldanha Bay, the focus was placed on the measurement of the load of the dust particles and the content of the dust particles. The load can be defined as the concentration of PM_{2.5} (in µg m⁻³). In contrast, the focus of the content is especially defined by the risks of metals and pathogens in the dust. Due to the industrial activities in this area, the dust likely contains potentially toxic metals such as Pb, Cr, and Mn. Pathogens would include microbial organisms such as bacteria, fungi, and viruses.

To evaluate the potential health risk, the focus was placed on the following strategy:

- Compare the PM_{2.5} concentration to national and international standards
- Determine the health risks of the metal content in the dust
- Determine the microbial community in the air and the presence of any pathogens

The PM_{2.5} concentration is generally included in the assessment of the air quality, and both national standards set by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) and international standards by the WHO were used in this study (see section 3.8.1). The health risks associated with the airborne metals were determined using the model from the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) (see section 3.8.2). The

focus was on the metals that are known to have a potential impact on human health, as shown in Table 1. For the pathogens, the microbial community associated with the dust particles was analysed. Combining knowledge on microbial communities and metal content in dust is a novel approach, especially in the specific setting of an industrial region. This study is described in section 3.6.

2.1.3 Ocean impact

This objective was to determine whether dust collected from the Saldanha Bay area could inhibit or stimulate phytoplankton growth in the coastal waters of southern Africa. To address this, three incubation experiments were conducted using marine phytoplankton communities collected from the coastal waters of the Western Cape, South Africa. During the incubation experiments, a pre-defined amount of dust from Saldanha Bay was added to the phytoplankton assemblage. The experiments were designed to investigate the response of phytoplankton to the metals, minerals, and nutrients in the dust and to evaluate potential adverse impacts (for details, see Section 3.7).

2.2 Previous work and ongoing efforts

Figure 6 provides an overview of the evolution of the project and the sampling and analyses that were conducted. The work completed in 2025 built on the ongoing work from 2023 and 2024, which is presented in Vos et al. [39,40,42,43]. For the dust monitoring, initial efforts included the installation of the first sensor in 2023 and a second one in 2024. In these years, the sensors were validated, and five new low-cost sensors were developed (see Section 3.1). For the passive sampling, the work included the ongoing sampling and analysis of the dust samples

Figure 6. Schematic overview of the different activities on the dust characteristics and impacts surrounding Saldanha Bay from 2023 till now.

(Section 3.2). For the active sampling, test runs were completed in 2024, and the active sampling was performed in April 2025 (Section 3.3). The soil and wipe sampling, the microbial, and ocean impact experiments were developed and completed in 2025 (Sections 3.4 to 3.7).

The Saldanha Bay Municipality has been monitoring the air pollution in the area since 2014. From January 2015 to September 2018, the hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations at Vredenburg were assessed. The details of this data are presented in Vos et al. [39]. From 2016 onwards, this monitoring includes the monthly assessment of dust that is deposited in seven so-called “dust buckets”. Detailed description of the measurements and the dataset can be found on <https://sbm.gov.za/environmental/>. From this dust, the depositional flux can be calculated (in mg day⁻¹ m⁻²). Furthermore, the concentration of the Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, and Pb in the dust is measured (in mg kg⁻¹), which can then be transformed into the depositional flux of these metals (in mg day⁻¹ m⁻²).

These previous results showed that the average PM_{2.5} concentrations in

Vredenburg, a town near the industrial hub, were relatively low (7.1 µg m⁻³) compared to national and international standards, though short-term spikes sometimes exceeded health guidelines. Figure 7 shows the annual deposition fluxes of five measured metals derived from this long-term municipal monitoring effort. As described previously in Vos et al. [43], the deposition fluxes indicated a general increase in the quantity of deposited Fe, Mn, and Zn from 2016 to 2024 that, however, was less consistent for Cu and Pb (Figure 7). Even though we cannot ascertain the exact cause of this increase observed for Fe, Mn, and Zn, it is plausible that this is associated with the expansion of industrial activities. The return of Pb to higher depositional fluxes towards 2024 (Figure 7) is of additional concern. While the calculated health risk indices for both adults and children remained below critical thresholds, children were found to be more vulnerable, and some metals were close to levels that could pose health risks if emissions increased [43]. Overall, Vos et al. [43] concluded that current air quality in the area does not present high immediate health risks, but industrial emissions do contribute to dust containing toxic metals.

Figure 7. The average annual metal deposition fluxes of Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, and Pb from 2016 to 2024 by the seven dust buckets that are managed by the Saldanha Bay Municipality. This data can be found on <https://sbm.gov.za/environmental/>.

3. Approaches and methodology

The methods from this study include a range of monitoring, sampling, and experimental methods, as shown in Figure 4, Figure 5, and Figure 6. These efforts are grouped into the following:

1. PM_{2.5} monitoring
2. Passive sampling
3. Active sampling
4. Soil and wipe sampling
5. Microbial measurements

The methodologies will be discussed in sections 3.1 to 3.6, and the sampling locations are shown in Figure 8. Here, the focus was on the towns in proximity to the industrial area: Saldanha, Langebaan, and Vredenburg. Also, some sampling was

done within the industrial area, whereby the main sampling was conducted around the Industrial Development Zone (IDZ). Lastly, the areas further north of the study area were included in the analyses, including the town of St. Helena Bay, due to the mainly southerly wind direction, which would transport potentially harmful particles in the northern direction [39]. For the soil and wipe sampling, it was possible to perform measurements before the rest of the sampling activities. The metals that this study focuses on are shown in Table 1.

Figure 8. Map of the study area and the different sampling and monitoring locations.

3.1 PM_{2.5} monitoring

To represent the dust load, we focus on the PM_{2.5} concentration as a better representation of the fine inhalable dust emission. This study relied on a number of low-cost PM_{2.5} sensors, both the globally used PurpleAir sensor [44–46] and two types of sensors that were developed at the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering at Stellenbosch University. The low-cost sensors allow for the measurement of the PM_{2.5} concentration at multiple locations, which gives a more accurate assessment of the dust concentration and the potential risks. As described by a number of studies, such a sensor can give reliable PM_{2.5} data. However, the sensors appear more useful for the atmospheric conditions, such as humidity [45,46]. To validate the sensor,

a validation experiment was set up in June and July and is described further in section 3.1.

3.1.1 PM_{2.5} sensors

The Saldanha Bay Municipality measured the PM_{2.5} concentration from 2015 to 2018. To continue this monitoring effort, we installed a PurpleAir sensor, which is a sensor that measures the PM_{2.5} concentration at a 2-minute interval. From 2023 onwards, a PurpleAir sensor was installed in Vredenburg, the results of which were reported in a previous BIOGRIP report [40,42]. In addition, a sensor (Figure 9b) built by Rita van der Walt from the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering at Stellenbosch University was installed on 26/09/2024. This sensor logged the estimated particulate

Figure 9. Example of the $PM_{2.5}$ sensors used at the Saldanha Bay Municipality: The PurpleAir (a), the dust sensor developed by Rita van der Walt (b), and the new dust sensors developed by Christopher Erasmus (c).

matter values and measured number concentrations to an SD card at 1-minute intervals. Both sensors were removed on 13/06/2025 for validation measurements. Furthermore, five new $PM_{2.5}$ sensors were developed by Christopher Erasmus from the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Stellenbosch University (Figure 9c). These sensors measure the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration at a 10-minute interval and have solar panels and an internal battery, allowing for measurements without relying on a constant input of electricity. Furthermore, they have the potential to transmit the data via a gateway, which allows for remote assessment of the measurements and sensor activity. All three sensors rely on $PM_{2.5}$ measurements by the PMS5003 sensor. Lastly, all three sensors allow for an assessment of the temperature and humidity, values that could potentially interfere with the $PM_{2.5}$ measurements [46–48].

3.1.2 Validation measurements

To validate the new sensors and determine any corrections for the $PM_{2.5}$ measurements, a comparison was made of the following low-cost sensors:

- 5 sensors developed by Christopher Erasmus
- 1 sensor developed by Rita van der Walt
- 5 PurpleAir sensors

These sensors were installed for approximately two weeks at two different governmental air quality monitoring stations. Sensors were installed from 17/06/2025 to 31/06/2025 at the Maitland station and from 01/07/2025 to 15/07/2025 at the Worcester station. Both stations are fitted with a calibrated $PM_{2.5}$ sensor, which measures the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration (among other air quality values) at 10-minute intervals. By comparing the data produced by the different sensors, including the temperature, humidity, and precipitation, the accuracy of these sensors can be determined, and a correction factor can be developed.

3.2 Passive sampling

Passive sampling allows for the collection of dust without relying on access to electricity. After sampling, the metal content of the dust can be measured. For the passive sampling, the Big Spring Number Eight (BSNE) samplers were used (Figure 10). These samplers move with the main wind direction and capture the horizontal dust flux. Most samplers were installed on residents' properties to prevent vandalism. In total, six BSNE samplers were used, and they were installed in the following locations: Vredenburg, Saldanha, the Industrial Development Zone (IDZ), St. Helena Bay, Blouwater Bay, and Diazville (Figure 8, Figure 11, and Supplementary section 1). In 2023, one sampler was installed at Langebaan, but this sampler was

removed due to the relocation of the residents. Furthermore, the sampler at Blouwater Bay was relocated due to construction in the area.

The collected dust is sampled after approximately two months, the mass is determined, and the samples are prepared for further analyses. In total, 49 samples were collected from 13/11/2023 to 29/10/2025. After sampling of the bulk dust, the remaining particles in the BSNEs were retrieved using small, HCl-cleaned brushes and ultrapure water. The dust samples were analysed for the elements in Table 1 using an Agilent 7900 Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS) at the Central Analytical Facilities (CAF) of Stellenbosch University. The metal content is presented as mg metal per kg dust (mg kg^{-1}).

Figure 10. Schematic overview of the passive dust sampler, the Big Spring Number Eight (BSNE), from Vos et al. [40].

Figure 11. Picture of the BSNEs at the different locations: (a) is at St. Helena Bay, (b) is at Langebaan, (c) is at Saldanha, (d) is at the Industrial Development Zone (IDZ), (e) is at Vredenburg, (f) is the first location at Blouwater Bay, and (g) is the second location at Blouwater Bay, (also refer to Figure 8).

3.3 Active sampling

Active sampling relies on actively pumping air and gathering dust on a filter, allowing the concentration of dust and metals per volume of air to be determined (in mg m^{-3}). It also allows size-fractionation of the particulate matter, providing insight into the size distribution of dust and the chemical characteristics of each size class. The active sampling was performed using the Tisch High Volume Air Sampler (HVAS) (Figure 8 and Figure 12a). Due to the high cost of these samplers and the labour-intensive nature of the sampling process, the active sampling was only done in the IDZ from 14/04/2025 to 21/04/2025. Since this dataset only represents eight days of sampling, it does not allow a comprehensive assessment across the seasons. Furthermore, it must be considered that these measurements were taken in proximity to the potential emission sources rather than the residential areas and might not represent the daily exposure of residents. Sampling was conducted in the IDZ because previous monitoring in residential areas resulted in noise complaints from residents.

Sampling with the HVAS was performed with a flow rate of approximately $1.0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. Two types of sampling cassettes were used in sequence: the Whatman-41

plate and the cascade impactor. The Whatman-41 plate performs bulk dust collection on 12 replicate 47mm low ash cellulose ester filters (Whatman 41PN 1441-047 with Whatman 41 PN1441-866 backing filter) (Figure 12b). Collecting 12 replicate samples enables repeated measurements and facilitates multiple types of analyses on the same dust samples. The cascade impactor enables size fractionated sampling on slotted cellulose ester substrates (Tisch Environmental TE-230WH with Whatman 41 PN1441-866 backing filter) (Figure 12c). This sampling leads to a separation of different size classes onto different filters during sampling (Figure 12d).

Both the Whatman-41 filters and the cellulose filters were cleaned with 1% (v/v) HCl, as recommended by the international programme GEOTRACES, which aims to improve our understanding of biogeochemical cycles and large-scale distribution of trace elements [49]. Each sampling cycle lasts 24 hours, resulting in 8 sampling cycles: 4 cycles with the Whatman plate and 4 with the size fractionated sampling. Supplementary section 2 shows the filter, sampling time and sampling dates of the different cycles. Similarly to the dust collected through the passive sampling approach (Section 3.2), the filter samples were analysed for metal content (Table 1) using an Agilent 7900 Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS) at the Central Analytical Facilities (CAF) of Stellenbosch University.

Figure 12. The Tisch High Volume Air Sampler (HVAS) installed at the IDZ, wrapped in black bags to protect the sampler against the corrosive conditions in this area (a), the Whatman plate with filters after 24 hours of sampling at the IDZ (b), a slotted filter on the cascade impactor after 24 hours of sampling, showing the collected dust (C), schematic diagram describing the different stages and size fractions of the cascade impactor and their relevance (d).

3.4 Soil sampling

The soil sampling was conducted from 14/04/2025 to 19/04/2025 as an extension of the passive and active dust sampling to gain insight into the spatial variability in the distribution of toxic metals. It also provides an initial assessment of the potential environmental contamination from industries within the Saldanha Bay Municipality. A total of 34 samples were collected across the municipal area, as illustrated in Figure 8. All instruments used, namely a stainless-steel auger, stainless steel trowel and plastic bucket, were disinfected using ethanol before sampling and between each sample site to prevent cross-contamination.

The samples were collected to a depth of 20cm below the surface. Each composite sample consisted of five sub-samples taken two meters from the central sample, forming a "+" pattern. The vegetation collected during the sampling was removed on-site. The bucket and trowel were used to mix and homogenise the sample on site before storing it in zip-lock bags for transportation.

In the laboratories at Stellenbosch University, the samples were prepared for analysis by quartering, coning, drying and sieving each sample into three size fractions:

- <0.053mm (silt + clay)
- ≥0.053mm and <0.25mm (silt to medium sand)
- ≥0.25mm and <2mm (medium to coarse sand)

Thus far, of the 34 samples, 10 priority samples sieved into 3 size fractions each were selected for ICP-MS analyses based on level of interest, land-use types, distance from BSNE samplers and distance from other points. The soil samples were analysed for metal content using an Agilent 7900 Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS). For additional details, refer to section 3.2.

To provide a preliminary assessment of the potential environmental impact

of these metals in the soil, the metal content (in mg kg⁻¹) is compared with the maximum concentration prescribed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) guidelines (Table 2). This comparison evaluates whether certain metals could have an adverse effect on the environment. A more extensive analysis of the soil samples will be included in the MSc thesis of Anesu Karadzandima at the end of 2026 and the PhD thesis of Kereemang Gaoaaga at the end of 2027.

Table 2. The maximum concentration standard for residential and industrial soil as recommended by the US EPA [41]. See Section 3.8.3 for a discussion on the oxidation states used for As and Cr (the latter represented as Cr (VI) for these standards).

Abr.	Contaminant	Resident Soil (mg kg ⁻¹)	Industrial Soil (mg kg ⁻¹)
Al	Aluminium	7.7E+4	1.1E+6
V	Vanadium	3.9E+2	5.8E+3
Cr (VI)	Chromium(VI)	3.0E-1	6.3E+0
Mn	Manganese	1.8E+3	2.6E+4
Fe	Iron	5.5E+4	8.2E+5
Co	Cobalt	2.3E+1	3.5E+2
Ni	Nickel	6.7E+2	8.1E+3
Cu	Copper	3.1E+3	4.7E+4
Zn	Zinc	2.3E+4	3.5E+5
As	Arsenic (Inorganic)	6.8E-1	3.0E+0
Se	Selenium	3.9E+2	5.8E+3
Sr	Strontium	4.7E+4	7.0E+5
Mo	Molybdenum	3.9E+2	5.8E+3
Cd	Cadmium	7.1E+0	1.0E+2
Sn	Tin	4.7E+4	7.0E+5
Sb	Antimony	3.1E+1	4.7E+2
Ba	Barium	1.5E+4	2.2E+5
Hg	Mercury	1.1E+1	4.6E+1
Pb	Lead	4.0E+2	8.0E+2

3.5 Wipes

To determine the potential exposure to metals in dust by residents in public areas, the dust that was deposited on public benches in the Saldanha Bay Municipality was measured. Similar to the soil samples, this data gives insight into the spatial variability of potentially toxic metals. The locations of the benches sampled in the Saldanha Bay Municipality are shown in Figure 8. Polyvinyl alcohol fabric (GRI PVA FABRIC) is widely used to sample dust on hard surfaces in occupational health and industrial contamination settings. Commonly known as 'Ghost Wipes', they dissolve completely during laboratory digestions, enabling the quantification of metal concentrations in the collected dust.

To prepare the wipes for sampling, the wipes were each placed in a petri dish and dried for 72 hours to obtain an accurate

weight of each wipe. To sample, a wipe was sprayed with ultrapure water and used to sample a 15 cm * 15 cm area in a concentric square pattern marked by a pre-cut template (Figure 13). The wipe was then folded in half, with the contaminated side inward, and reused to wipe the same area. This process was repeated until the wipe had been used three times on the same surface. In the laboratory, the wipes were dried under the fume hood for 72 hours. The dry wipes were weighed to calculate the mass of dust collected. Each wipe was then digested in HNO₃ and H₂O₂ and analysed using the Agilent 7900 Inductively Coupled Plasma Spectrometry (ICP-MS) at Stellenbosch University, Central Analytical Facilities, for the selected trace metals, see section 3.1. A more extensive analysis of the soil samples will be presented in the master's thesis of Anesu Karadzandima and the PhD thesis of Kereemang Gaoaaga.

Figure 13. Images of the dust sampling in Saldanha using ghost wipes. a) wipes were sprayed with ultra-pure water before wiping surfaces, b) a pre-cut template was used to demarcate the area for the collection of dust deposited on public benches.

3.6 Microbial content

Particle-associated pathogens represent an additional health risk posed by dust, but they are generally not included in standard air pollution health risk assessments. In this context, pathogens refer to micro-organisms such as bacteria, fungi, and viruses that can be harmful to human health. To gain new insights into airborne pathogens, we initiated a collaboration with the Department of Microbiology at Stellenbosch University, which provides a novel perspective on the interactions between airborne metals and micro-organisms.

To detect pathogens and examine links between microbes and dust metal content, microbial samples from four sites around Saldanha Bay were analysed.

Four locations were chosen to perform the sampling, namely, IDZ, Vredenburg, Saldanha, and Blouwater Bay (Figure 8). In addition, four control samples were taken from sites of low industrial impact in the areas around Stellenbosch, Malmesbury, and Wiesenhof Nature Reserve. This sampling was done using two SASS3100 Dry Air Samplers, which hold two different filters in parallel (Figure 14). A Whatman-41 filter was used to analyse the metal content (see also Section 3.3), and a HEPA-style electret filter was used simultaneously to analyse the micro-organisms. For each location, two sampling cycles of five hours were performed. The metal content of the dust was measured using the same analyses as those presented in section 3.3. The microbial samples from this study are still being analysed, and the results will not be presented in this report.

Figure 14. Images of the microbial sampling efforts in Saldanha Bay showing the installation of the samplers in Saldanha (a), and the installed sampling setup at the IDZ (b).

3.7 Ocean impact assessment

To determine the influence of Saldanha dust on the marine environment, different concentrations of Saldanha dust were added to phytoplankton laboratory incubations to represent normal, above normal, and high dust deposition conditions, based on dust amounts measured in the area. Phytoplankton communities collected from Table Bay, South Africa, were used. The overview of the setup for the incubation studies can be found in Supplementary section 3. Before starting, the larger particles were removed from the seawater, nutrient and metal levels were confirmed, and macro- nutrients were supplied for optimal phytoplankton growth. The dust was added to ultrapure water, placed in an ultrasonic bath to break up particles and support leaching. This initial stock solution was then filtered, analysed for dissolved metal content, and predefined concentrations added to the phytoplankton incubation vials. The incubations were kept at a cool temperature (16° C) aligned with the source ocean water temperatures with a day–night photoperiod (12 hours light and 12 hours dark) to mimic natural conditions. During the incubations, the vials are gently mixed to keep cells in suspension, and the growth was monitored for approximately 16 days using daily fluorescence readings. Samples were taken at the beginning and at the end to measure changes in chlorophyll-a, which is an indicator of the biomass of the phytoplankton, metals,

and the microscopic determination of phytoplankton species. The extensive description of the methodology is shown in Supplementary section 3. A more extensive analysis of the ocean impact assessment is presented in the PhD thesis of Emtia Wium and the MSc thesis of Zanika De Mon.

3.8 Health risk assessment

3.8.1 PM_{2.5} concentrations

The impact of dust particles depends on the load of dust particles and the content of the dust particles. Typically, the concentration of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} is referred to in air quality assessments (in mg m⁻³ or µg m⁻³). PM_{2.5} is generally regarded as the most reliable standard for assessing anthropogenic air pollution and is measured using dust sensors. [50–53]. National and international health standards exist for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations, specifying both maximum daily average and maximum annual average limits. (Table 3). As such, the World Health Organisation (WHO) refers to maximum values above which “negative health impacts from particulate matter can be expected”. Globally, these conditions are rarely reached [54]. The South African national standard, defined by the NAAQS, was initially proposed in 2004, with an updated version set to take effect from 2030 onward. In this report, we use the current NAAQS standard, the 2030 NAAQS standard, and the WHO standard to highlight the potential health risks from the PM_{2.5} (Table 3).

*Table 3. The maximum allowable PM_{2.5} concentration prescribed by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) and the World Health Organisation (WHO). *The daily average has a frequency of exceedance of four, meaning that the daily value can be crossed four times per year and still be considered within the guidelines.*

	Current NAAQS standard	NAAQS standard in 2030	WHO standard
Daily average*	40 µg m ⁻³	20 µg m ⁻³	15 µg m ⁻³
Annual average	20 µg m ⁻³	15 µg m ⁻³	5 µg m ⁻³

3.8.2 Health risks that arise from exposure to airborne metals

This report focuses on a wide range of metals that are associated with dust and that are known to have a potential risk for human health (Table 4). South African national guidelines only include a standard of $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ Pb, while no standards have been established for the other airborne metals. Hence, to calculate the potential health risks from airborne metals, a model from the US EPA was used. This model assumes the chemical daily intake (CDI, in $\text{mg day}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$) of metals via inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact. The CDI is determined for children and adults separately, whereby children in general have a higher intake per body weight [43]. Furthermore, per location, the so-called "maximum exposure" is calculated to represent the highest concentration that people could be exposed to, rather than the average concentration. The respective parameters and calculations are summarised in Supplementary section 4. The estimation of the CDI of metals is compared to the Reference Dose (RfD) supplied by the US EPA [41] (Table 4). The Hazardous index, which is the non-carcinogenic risk,

and the carcinogenic risk, is calculated following equation 1:

$$1) \text{ Hazard index} = \frac{\text{CDI}_{\text{inh,dermal,ing}} * \text{BAF}}{\text{RfD}}$$

$$2) \text{ Carcinogenic Risk} = \sum \text{CDI}_{\text{inh,dermal,ing}} * \text{BAF} * \text{SF}$$

Where BAF is the bioaccumulation factor, and SF stands for the slope factor (Table 4). A Hazard Index above 1 indicates that there are significant health risks, whereas a lower Hazard Index represents a lower presumed non-carcinogenic risk. For the carcinogenic risk, a threshold value of 10^{-4} is taken to represent the threshold for a significant health risk.

In addition to the calculation of the hazard index (non-carcinogenic risk) and carcinogenic risks, the measured metal concentration in the air (as retrieved from the active sampling, see section 3.3) is compared to the standard recommended by the US EPA (Table 4). These air quality standards cover most metals and both residential and industrial environments. Since the metal concentration in the air is only known for the IDZ, these values are not incorporated for the health risk assessment of the other residential areas.

Table 4. The standards described by the US EPA according to their 2023 standards [41]. Here, SF stands for the slope factor, and RfD stands for the reference dose.

Abr.	SF (mg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	RfD (mg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	BAF (%)	Resident Air (µg m ⁻³)	Industrial Air (µg m ⁻³)
Al		1.0E+0		5.2E+0	2.2E+1
V		5.0E-3	11.2	1.0E-1	4.4E-1
Cr (VI)	5.0E-1	3.0E-3	5.83	1.2E-5	1.5E-4
Mn		2.4E-2	47.6	5.2E-2	2.2E-1
Fe		7.0E-1	3.88		
Co		3.0E-4	22.1	3.1E-4	1.4E-3
Ni		1.1E-2	15.7	1.1E-2	4.7E-2
Cu		4.0E-2	29.8		
Zn		3.0E-1	60.1		
As	1.5E+0	3.0E-4	38.8	6.5E-4	2.9E-3
Se		5.0E-3		2.1E+1	8.8E+1
Sr		6.0E-1			
Mo		5.0E-3		2.1E+0	8.8E+0
Cd		1.0E-4	74.5	1.6E-3	6.8E-3
Sn		6.0E-1			
Sb		4.0E-4		3.1E-1	1.3E+0
Ba		2.0E-1		5.2E-1	2.2E+0
Pb		3.5E-3	47.0	1.5E-1	

3.8.3 Oxidation states of Cr and As

For most health and environmental impact assessments, certain metals have specific oxidation states that are much more toxic than other oxidation states of the same metals. In this study, the metals with important oxidation states are Chromium (Cr) and Arsenic (As). For Cr, Cr(VI) is much more soluble, mobile, and toxic than Cr(III), but minerals containing Cr(VI) are also rarer. Due to this toxicity, most guidelines for Cr specifically focus on Cr(VI) levels. For As, the trivalent form (As(III)) is far more toxic to humans than the pentavalent form (As(V)). In the US EPA guidelines, no differentiation is made between these oxidation states and only the total As is considered. Furthermore, the ICP-MS measurement presents the total chromium (Cr) and total arsenic (As) concentration without distinguishing between their chemical forms (speciation). This difference is also discussed in Vos et al. [43].

Cr(VI) can constitute up to 20% of airborne chromium in some urban areas [55]. Fine particles (PM_{2.5}) are often enriched in Cr(VI), where it contributes up to 50% of total Cr in city centres and 30–40% near road traffic [56,57]. Based on previous studies [58,59], we therefore assume that Cr(VI) represents 25% of the total measured chromium in our health risk calculations, following Vos et al. [43]. As(V) is usually the dominant form (50–99%) in airborne particles in urban, industrial, and remote settings [60–63]. However, in urban areas, the proportion of As(III) increases in fine particles and can even dominate in PM_{2.5} [64–66]. In line with US EPA guidelines, the total arsenic concentration was used for the health risk calculations, assuming most arsenic is present as As(V). However, this may underestimate actual risks, and future research should focus on measuring the oxidation states to create a more accurate risk assessment.

4. Results

4.1 PM_{2.5} monitoring

Figure 15 shows the daily PM_{2.5} measured by the Purple Air sensor in the IDZ area, and the PM_{2.5} sensor that was developed at Stellenbosch University was installed in Vredenburg for the period from July 2023 to July 2025. This data showed a total

average PM_{2.5} concentration of 6.21 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and 8.18 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Vredenburg and IDZ, respectively. This data is compared with the national and international air quality guidelines. As had been reported in 2024 by Vos et al. [40,42], the yearly average remains below the NAAQS guidelines, but the daily averages do exceed the guidelines threshold occasionally.

Figure 15. The daily PM_{2.5} concentration measured by the PM_{2.5} sensors developed at Stellenbosch University in the IDZ and the PurpleAir in Vredenburg.

Key takeaway:

- The Vredenburg and IDZ sensors measured an average PM_{2.5} concentration of 6.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and 8.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively, which is within the guidelines for annual average concentrations.
- Some daily peaks exceed the recommended threshold.

4.2 Passive sampling

Figure 16 shows the concentration of metals in the dust (in mg kg⁻¹) measured from 2023 to 2025. This data is grouped by type of element and by location. Similar to the data from Vos et al. [39], the highest concentrations are Al, Zn, and Fe. The metal concentrations in dust

vary by site, with higher levels at IDZ and Vredenburg. However, not all metals vary consistently. Compared to a suite of global dust particles, especially the Mn content, but also Cu, Co, and Ni content in the Saldanha Bay dust, was elevated [43].

Figure 16. The metal concentration of the dust sampled by the BSNE from 13/11/2023 to 29/10/2025 from the different monitoring stations.

Key takeaway:

- Large variations in dust metal concentrations were observed, with Fe and Zn generally recording the highest levels.

4.3 Active sampling

The concentration of the metals in the air was measured at the IDZ in April 2025 for both bulk dust and size fractionated particles. Similar to the passive sampling, the concentration of Fe and Zn in the bulk dust is high, and in addition, high concentrations of Mn were observed (Figure 17). The data furthermore show a notable variation of Pb, Cd, and Cu. The Mn and Cr concentrations exceed the US EPA industrial standards (Figure 19). Co, As, Cd, and Pb concentrations are below the guidelines for industrial areas but

above the standards for residential areas. The concentrations of all other metals (Al, V, Ni, Se, Mo, Sb, Ba) were low and did not exceed residential thresholds, despite being measured at an industrial site. Guidelines for Fe and Pb in industrial zones are not currently available. Most metals are associated with the smaller particles (<7.2 μm) (Figure 20). On average, approximately half of the metals are associated with particles larger than 3.0 μm . This demonstrated the importance of accounting for smaller particles when assessing the transport and burden of potentially toxic metals.

Figure 17. The concentration of metals in the air associated with the bulk dust was measured by active sampling at the IDZ. Here, Period 1 represents the sampling from 14/04/2025 to 15/04/2025, period 2 represents the sampling from 16/04/2025 to 17/04/2025, period 3 represents the sampling from 18/04/2025 to 19/04/2025, and period 4 represents the sampling from 20/04/2025 to 21/04/2025.

Figure 18. The dust concentration measured at the IDZ by a High-Volume Air Sampler (HVAS) relative to the standards set by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA). These graphs compare the measured concentration to the industrial standard (a), which would be most relevant for this area, and to the residential standard (b). The black line represents the US EPA standard.

Figure 19. The relative concentration of metals in different dust particle size classes.

Key takeaway:

- Similar to the metal content in the dust, the concentration of Fe and Zn in the air is the highest out of all the measured metals. Mn also showed notable high concentrations.
- The concentration of Mn and Cr in the air exceeds the US EPA [41] recommended maximum values for industrial areas.
- Generally, metal content is higher in particles smaller than 7.2 µm.

4.4 Soil and wipe samples

The metal concentrations in the size fractionated soil particles are presented in Figure 20. In contrast to the dust particles, the concentration of the Al is high, whereas Zn and Mn are less prominent. These differences are expected due to the influence that the geology has on soil compositions. Similar to the dust particles, there are generally more metals, such as Al, Mn, Fe, Zn, As, and Pb, associated with fine (clay and silt-sized) particles. Since clay and silt particles have a larger surface area compared to their weight due to their elongated shape and negative surface charges, more metal ions are associated with such fine dust particles. In addition, fine particles commonly consist of clay minerals and metal oxides that contain more metals.

The metal concentrations in the soil were compared to the US EPA thresholds recommended for residential and industrial areas. Cr and As both exceed the US EPA threshold recommended for industrial areas, whereas the other metals did not exceed their respective thresholds. Notably, these metals occur in oxidation states that are very toxic (as discussed in section 3.8.3). Future research on the environmental impact and contamination of soils should aim at understanding the characteristics of Cr and As in the soil and the sources (natural and anthropogenic) of these metals.

The metals show very different spatial variations (Supplementary section 5). Mn occurs in peak concentrations along the train tracks and Mn ore operations, while Pb and Cr occur in peak concentrations around Vredenburg and Saldanha. This emphasises the multiple sources of metals in the soil.

Figure 20. The metal concentration in soil, grouped per grain size class, as measured across the Saldanha Bay Municipality (a), and the comparison of these values with industrial standards (b) and residential standards (c). Here, Cr(VI) (as shown in b and c) is defined as 25% of the total Cr (as shown in a).

Figure 21 shows the results from the ghost wipe samples, presenting the metal concentration sampled per cm² of a public bench. Similar to the soil samples, the wipe samples showed a specific high concentration of Al and Fe. By splitting the data into the three towns they were sampled from (Saldanha, Vredenburg,

and Langebaan), a general assessment of the concentration differences can be made. In Vredenburg, the concentration of Mn, Fe, Zn, Mo, and Cd is significantly higher than that of Saldanha and Langebaan (determined using an ANOVA test and an alpha value of 0.05).

Figure 21. The elemental mass per cm² as sampled by the wipes from a surface of 15 by 15 cm group per metal (a) and per metal and sampling location (b).

Key takeaway:

- In both soils and on public benches, Al and Fe are the most abundant metals.
- Compared to industrial soil standards from the US EPA [41], the Cr and As exceed the soil standards, which emphasises the need for understanding the oxidation state of these metals.
- All other metals remained below both the industrial and residential standards.
- The metal concentration shows large spatial variability, which appears to differ per metal.

4.5 Ocean impact experiments

The effects of Saldanha dust on local phytoplankton were investigated at three treatment levels, namely normal (2 mg L^{-1}), above normal (2.6 mg L^{-1}), and high (3.8 mg L^{-1}), across three incubation experiments (A–C, see Supplementary section 3). The trend in fluorescence showed that control samples displayed normal phytoplankton growth, while dust treatments generally followed similar patterns, although occasional short-term fluctuations in peak fluorescence

were observed. Statistical analyses confirmed day-to-day variability but did not reveal consistent growth stimulation or suppression linked to added dust.

The preliminary chlorophyll-a concentrations indicated that dust treatments frequently led to increased chlorophyll-a concentrations relative to controls by the seventh day, suggesting a stimulatory effect rather than toxicity. Only the highest dust treatment (3.8 mg L^{-1}) in the first experiment showed slight signs of inhibition.

Key takeaway:

- The experiments that test the response of phytoplankton to the dust from Saldanha showed a positive response from the phytoplankton, indicating that the dust likely has a growth stimulating, rather than a toxic effect.

5. Discussion

5.1 Dust load and metal content

The PM_{2.5} monitoring showed a generally low PM_{2.5} concentration of 6.21 µg m⁻³ at Vredenburg and 8.18 µg m⁻³ at the IDZ.

The results of the metal content from the different sampling efforts are shown in Table 5, together with a comparison of the US EPA air and soil standards. The Fe and Zn concentrations were highest in the dust and per volume air, with Mn also being a prominent metal in the air. Metal concentrations in soil and dust on public benches were highest for Al and Fe. Cr and

Mn levels exceeded recommended air concentration standards. Co, As, Cd, and Pb exceeded the threshold for residential areas. In contrast, only Cr(VI) and As exceeded the standard for industrial soils, whereby we note that the oxidation states of these metals might lead to an over- or underestimation of the potential impact of these metals (see section 3.8.3).

These results indicate that different methodologies, such as active or passive dust sampling, soil sampling, or wipe sampling, yield varying relative estimates of dust load and metal concentrations, emphasising the importance of an extensive assessment.

Table 5. The mean concentrations of metals as measured by different sampling approaches. *Represents the correction from total Cr to Cr(VI) by calculating the 25% of this value.

Metal	Mean dust (mg kg ⁻¹)	Mean air (mg m ⁻³)	Mean soil (mg kg ⁻¹)	Mean wipes (mg cm ⁻²)	Exceedance air standard	Soil Standard
Al	40124.60	4.76E-4	13795.37	1.02E-3		
V	30.06	2.86E-6	16.94	3.10E-6		
Cr	530.89	1.94E-6	133.38	4.44E-6	Industrial*	Residential*
Mn	1881.91	5.73E-4	311.82	6.52E-5	Industrial	
Fe	38253.75	5.40E-3	10515.43	1.65E-3		
Co	58.51	4.79E-7	2.02	6.65E-7	Residential	
Ni	287.71	2.02E-6	7.03	1.81E-6		
Cu	88.47	2.09E-5	11.97	9.94E-6		
Zn	11042.40	5.75E-4	57.78	1.05E-4		
As	8.67	8.69E-7	2.34	2.08E-6	Residential	Residential
Se	1.08	4.23E-7	0.35	4.05E-8		
Sr	166.66	1.14E-5	138.21	1.22E-5		
Mo	8.52	1.47E-7	3.93	7.85E-8		
Cd	2.56	1.12E-6	0.29	7.98E-8	Residential	
Sn	40.41	5.24E-7	2.37	6.02E-7		
Sb	2.31	3.22E-7	0.16	1.22E-6		
Ba	197.58	2.27E-5	60.37	9.91E-6		
Pb	206.44	1.15E-4	31.27	3.26E-5	Residential	

5.2 Health risk

As mentioned previously, the risk of dust is determined by the load of dust in the air and the content of the dust. Here, the dust load is defined using the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration, and the health risks based on the presence of potentially toxic metals. As discussed in Section 4.1, the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration was relatively low and generally followed national guidelines. However, the dust appeared to be enriched in Mn and Cr compared to other studies and EPA guidelines (see Sections 4.2 and 4.3). To determine the potential non-carcinogenic health risks, the hazard index of individual metals was calculated. The 95% upper confidence limit (UCL) of all the measured metal concentrations, and per measurement site, was calculated. The CDI was then estimated and compared to the reference dose as prescribed by the US EPA [41].

Each metal's calculated hazard index of the whole dataset is shown in Figure 22, and the hazard index of the individual

monitoring sites is shown in Figure 23. The hazard index derived from the comprehensive dataset could be a better overall representation since residents are likely to travel within their town and municipality. The hazard index of the whole dataset approaches the recommended threshold for Mn, Co, and Zn for children. When considering the hazard index for children of individual stations, the threshold of the metals Al, Mn, Co, Zn, Cd, and Pb is exceeded by different stations. Despite the clear differences in health risks of specific metals at individual stations, every station shows a significant health risk for one or more metals. For adults, the risk of Al, Mn, Zn, and Pb is approaching the threshold levels. There is only a significant health risk for Zn at the IDZ. Lastly, the Carcinogenic Risk of Cr(VI) and As is shown in Figure 24. In Vredenburg and St. Helena Bay, the element Cr(VI) exceeded the recommended threshold of 10^{-4} for children. These results highlight the potential risks posed by different metals, especially in specific regions.

Figure 22. The Hazard Index from different metals and the threshold that indicates whether a significant health risk could be posed.

Figure 23. The hazard index of individual locations for adults (a) and children (b).

Figure 24. The carcinogenic risks of Cr(VI) and As determined for the complete dataset (all) and for the individual locations.

Key takeaway:

- The PM_{2.5} concentration itself shows a low risk.
- There is an indication for a potential health risk posed by Mn, Co, and Zn.

5.3 Ocean impact

Overall, under the experimental conditions described herein, the dust collected in the greater Saldanha area was not harmful to phytoplankton but

rather enhanced photosynthetic activity and biomass accumulation. Toxic effects appear to be limited, sporadic, and only potentially associated with the highest dust load tested.

Key takeaway:

- The incubation experiments show that the dust from the Saldanha Bay area has a fertilising effect, rather than a toxic effect.

5.4 Ongoing and future work

5.4.1 Microbial measurements

The sampling efforts in April 2025, as described in Section 3.6, provided a preliminary dataset on both the microbial communities, including the pathogens, as well as the metal content of the dust. This data will give valuable insight into the relationship between the dust elemental content and the microbes which are present. It can also inform on potential adverse health effects related to the types of micro-organisms which are present in specific types of dust. The data is currently under preparation for publication in collaboration with the Department of Microbiology, see also Section 6.1.

5.4.2 Solubility measurements

Not all the trace metals present in the atmosphere can be dissolved into water. The solubility of trace metals depends upon the source and composition of the dust, as well as processes such as

oxidation and dissolution during their transport. Information on the solubility improves our understanding of the impact of atmospheric trace metals on the ecosystem. It can furthermore determine the influence on human health and the bio-available trace metals present in the dust samples. The bio-availability of metals helps us to understand the quantity of trace metals which can be absorbed in our body, and this can now be determined using the BAF values (as described in Section 3.8.2). Additional experiments using dissolution in ultrapure water are in progress to determine the quantity of metals that dissolve into water. Future work can focus on the dissolution of metals in more specific body fluids, such as blood, lymphatic fluids, or stomach acids, to improve the estimation of the BAF value and, therefore, the health risks.

5.4.3 Ocean experiments

Only three dust treatments were chosen for the incubation experiments. Here, the concentrations were chosen based on the information on dust fluxes in the

greater Saldanha area and the respective setup available at the time. For a more concise overview of the effect of Saldanha dust on marine phytoplankton, more dust treatments should be explored to determine at which concentrations statistically significant toxic effects are observed. With this information, the industrial air pollution in the area can be regulated. In addition, the three dust incubation experiments were conducted during June, July and August 2025, resulting in dust toxicity tests conducted on “winter” phytoplankton community compositions only. With the change of season, the phytoplankton community may likely shift to include other dominant species due to the change in water temperature and wind patterns. It is therefore advised to continue the incubation experiments throughout the other months, such as spring, summer and autumn, to ensure the dust treatments do not negatively affect the phytoplankton growth of the respective population.

5.4.4 Oxidation states

As described in Section 3.8.3, the oxidation states of metals can be of importance when it comes to considering the toxicity of the metal. Especially in the case of Cr and As, the oxidation states would be important to understand the impact of the metals on the environment and public health. Since As and Cr indicated a risk for the environment and public health, future measurements should address the quantification of these elemental oxidation states.

5.4.5 Public health survey

Future work should focus on gathering health data from residents living in the Saldanha Bay area. This data can give better insight into the true impact of the industries on health and extend our understanding of this impact beyond risk assessment. This work is expected to be extensive and require access to public health data and knowledge of public health research.

5.4.6 Source assessment and mitigation possibilities

So far, this research has indicated the possible health risks of the dust emitted from industrial activities around Saldanha Bay. Especially the emission of Al, Cr, Mn, Co, Zn, As, Cd, and Pb appears to be relevant. Next steps would be addressing the exact operations that would lead to significant emissions of these metals. Understanding the precise source of the potentially harmful metals would be the first step in exploring the opportunities for mitigating these emissions. Several studies have investigated mitigation possibilities at a wide range of industrial activities [67,67–70], also within South Africa. Developing these strategies requires collaboration with industries.

6. Additional information

6.1 Publications and reports

Published:

Vos, H.C., Vogel, E., von Holdt, J.R., Fister, W., Eckardt, F.D., Gugger, J.I., Hofstetter, E.C., Kuhn, N.J., 2025. Arid Shrubland: A growing dust source? *Aeolian Research* 74, 100998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeolia.2025.100998>

Vos, H.C., von Holdt, J.R., Merwe, H. van der, Samuels, I., Schmiedel, U., Jürgens, N., Krenz, J., Masubelele, M.L., Koovarjee, B., Fister, W., Eckardt, F.D., Cupido, C., Kuhn, N.J., Fietz, S., 2025. Land cover, drought, and dust emission in arid Succulent Karoo shrublands. *Aeolian Research* 74, 101006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeolia.2025.101006>

Vos, H.C.; Kanguuehi, K.; Toesie, R.; Ravenscroft, G.; Fietz, S. Variation and Health Risks of the Potentially Toxic Metals in Dust around an Industrial Hub. *Clean Air Journal* 2025, 35. <https://doi.org/10.17159/caj/2025/35/2.22227>

In preparation:

- Shipboard gaseous elemental mercury concentrations in the Cape Town port area, South Africa, compared to marine background concentrations (working title)
- Does an industrial environment favour the selection of pathogenic microbes? (working title)

6.2 Postgraduate students involved in the project

The following post-graduate students who are based at the Earth Science Department (SU) are currently working on this project for their respective degrees:

- Ms Anesu Karadzandima – Master's Thesis
- Ms Kereemang Gaoaaga – PhD Thesis
- Ms Zanika de Mon – Master's Thesis
- Ms Emtia Wium – PhD Thesis

6.3 Conferences and meetings attended

Goldschmidt 2025 Conference Prague

- Invited oral presentation: Dust from arid South Africa: A story of drought, mining, and land degradation
- Oral presentation: The health risks of the dust and potentially toxic metals around an industrial hub

57th Annual National Association for Clean Air (NACA)

- Poster presentation: The Potential Biomedical Effects of Dust in Saldanha Bay
- Oral presentation and Poster presentation: Geochemical characterisation and morphology of fine inhalable particles (PM) in residential areas of the Western Cape, South Africa

7th Annual Gauteng Environmental Research Symposium (GERS7)

- Oral presentation: The Potential Biomedical Effects of Dust in Saldanha Bay

Saldanha Bay Clean Air Association's State of the Atmosphere Report event

- Oral presentation: The health risks of the potentially toxic metals in dust around Saldanha Bay

Stakeholder meeting for the Cape West Coast Biosphere Reserve

- Oral presentation: The health risks of the potentially toxic metals in dust around Saldanha Bay

BIOGRIP workshop 2025

- Oral presentation: Methodology of dust sampling and monitoring

7th SANAP Symposium 2025

- Presentation: Micronutrient and pollutant trace elements at the air-sea interface of the Southern Ocean

6.4 Stakeholders

This project was executed in collaboration with the following stakeholders at the Saldanha Bay Municipality and Western Cape Government:

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Supplementary information

1. Passive sampling installation dates

Table 6. The location of the BSNE samplers and the start and end time of this sampling. The sampler at Blouwater Bay was due to construction in the area, causing a gap in the sampling data here. IDZ represents the Industrial Development Zone.

Location	Start	End
Langebaan	18/09/2023	8/02/2024
Saldanha	18/09/2023	Ongoing
Vredenburg	18/09/2023	Ongoing
St. Helena Bay	18/09/2023	Ongoing
Blouwater Bay - Location 1	18/09/2023	22/04/2024
Blouwater Bay - Location 2	09/05/2024	Ongoing
IDZ	8/02/2024	Ongoing
Diazville	14/04/2025	Ongoing

2. Active sampling dates

Table 7. A summary of the cycles from the active sampling, including the cycle number, the filter type, which was used, which includes the 47 mm filters, the cascade impactor sampling, and the start time and end time

Cycle	Filter type	Start date	Start time	End date	End time	Length
Cycle 1	Whatman 41	14-Apr	13:42	15-Apr	13:42	24:00:00
Cycle 2	Cascade	15-Apr	13:57	16-Apr	13:53	23:56:00
Cycle 3	Whatman 41	16-Apr	14:01	17-Apr	14:05	24:04:00
Cycle 4	Cascade	17-Apr	14:13	18-Apr	14:04	23:51:00
Cycle 5	Whatman 41	18-Apr	14:09	19-Apr	14:09	24:00:00
Cycle 6	Cascade	19-Apr	14:15	20-Apr	14:15	24:00:00
Cycle 7	Whatman 41	20-Apr	14:20	21-Apr	14:20	24:00:00
Cycle 8	Cascade	21-Apr	14:30	22-Apr	14:30	24:00:00

3. Ocean impact assessment

To determine the influence of Saldanha dust on the marine environment, different concentrations of Saldanha dust were added to phytoplankton communities. Three categories were chosen for the concentrations of the dust treatments. The dust concentration of the categories was determined by the investigation of previously published dust incubations on marine phytoplankton, as well as the dust deposition rate in the area, which was recorded as a range of 114 mg m⁻² day⁻¹ to 262 mg m⁻² day⁻¹ [40].

The "high deposition" scenario was altered to a ~20% increase above the upper range to simulate abnormally high deposition. Therefore, 165 mg m⁻² day⁻¹, 215 mg m⁻² day⁻¹ and 315 mg m⁻² day⁻¹ dust deposition fluxes were chosen, resulting in dust depositions of 0.10 mg/day, 0.13 mg/day and 0.19 mg/day, respectively. Incorporating these dust depositions into the volume of the test tubes utilised in the incubation experiments, each scenario resulted in 2 mg/L, 2.6 mg/L and 3.8 mg/L, respectively.

Table 8. Overview of the dust incubation experiments. The location where the seawater was collected, concentration of the mother stock of the dust, test tube numbers and corresponding dust additions per deposition rate are shown.

Experiment and location of phytoplankton collection	Category of dust deposition rate	Amount of dissolved dust added to the test tube (mg/L)
Experiment A: Table Bay 33°5153.46S, 18°2330.36E	Control	None
	Normal dust deposition	2 mg/L
	Above normal dust deposition	2.6 mg/L
	High dust deposition	3.8 mg/L
Experiment B: Table Bay 33°5155.36S, 18°2330.33E	Control	None
	Normal dust deposition	2 mg/L
	Above normal dust deposition	2.6 mg/L
	High dust deposition	3.8 mg/L
Experiment C: Table Bay 33°5154.44S, 18°2330.34E	Control	None
	Normal dust deposition	2 mg/L
	Above normal dust deposition	2.6 mg/L
	High dust deposition	3.8 mg/L

Surface seawater containing the natural phytoplankton community was collected off the coast of Table Bay, South Africa. All the equipment used for these experiments was acid-cleaned according to GEOTRACES protocols [49] (Figure 25). At Stellenbosch University, the seawater in the original container was swirled for a few seconds to ensure the phytoplankton cells were in suspension when pre-screened through the 200 µm mesh. Samples were taken for the ICPMS analysis for metal concentration determination in the seawater and nutrient determination (nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, silicate and additional ammonium). Afterwards, the pre-screened seawater was enriched with nutrients (phosphate (1 x 10⁻⁵ M NaH₂PO₄ · H₂O), nitrate (1 x 10⁻⁴ M NaNO₃) and silicate (1 x 10⁻⁴ M Na₂SiO₃ · 9H₂O)). Another set of samples was taken for ICPMS, nutrients, community composition, fluorescence and chlorophyll-a measurements. The remaining pre-screened, nutrient-rich seawater was decanted into the 60 mL test tubes at volumes of 50 mL.

Figure 25: Preparation required for dust incubation experiments. Seawater was sampled from Table Bay using a 20L carboy. It was decanted from the container through a 200 µm mesh into a 2L Nalgene bottle. Thereafter, ICPMS and nutrient samples were collected. Following this, nutrients ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaNO_3 and $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were added to the filtered seawater. Afterwards, ICPMS, nutrients, phytoplankton community, fluorescence and chlorophyll samples were sampled. At the end of the sampling, 50ml of the nutrient-enriched, mesh-filtered seawater was decanted into test tubes for incubation.

To prepare the dust solution, the dry BSNE dust was collected and stored in a centrifuge tube (Figure 26). On the first official day of the incubation, the dust was transferred from the centrifuge tube to a weighing boat with a known weight, with the use of plastic tweezers. The dust was weighed and transferred from the weighing boat to a new centrifuge tube via a known amount of ultra-pure water (UPW) and a pipette. The centrifuge tube was filled with UPW afterwards until the desired amount was present. Afterwards, the centrifuge tube containing the dust mixture was placed in a beaker with UPW, which was then placed in an ultrasonicator filled with tap water for 15 minutes. This was done to ensure the dust dissolves, releasing the maximum leachable metals from the particles. After the 15 minutes, the centrifuge tube was removed from the ultrasonicator and left to cool for ~5 minutes, whereafter it was filtered through a pre-cleaned 0.2 µm PVDF filter. A drop of 65% HNO_3 was added to the dust solution to ensure the metals within the

solution remain stable. From this dust solution, dilutions were made to ensure the final dust treatments amounted to the chosen concentrations, namely 2 mg/L, 2.6 mg/L and 3.8 mg/L.

Figure 26: Overview of dust solution preparation for incubation experiments. Dust from the Saldanha area was collected and weighed. It was transferred to a new centrifuge tube using UPW and a pipette and placed in an ultrasonicator for 15 minutes to ensure metals leach from the dust into the solution. The tube was left to cool, whereafter the solution was filtered. This filtered dust solution was treated with 65% HNO₃ to ensure the metals stay stable throughout the course of the incubation.

After the dust dilutions were prepared, 1 ml of the 2 mg/L and 3.8 mg/L solutions was added to 7 test tubes each, and 1 ml of the 2.6 mg/L solution to 3 test tubes. These test tubes were placed in a temperature-controlled (~15 °C) incubation chamber, receiving 12 hours of light and 12 hours of darkness (photoperiod) to mimic natural conditions. A rotation setting in the incubation chamber was utilised during the incubation duration to ensure the test tubes received the same light exposure. In addition, the test tubes were gently inverted every few hours to ensure the phytoplankton cells stayed in suspension.

The incubation period was determined as ~16 days, where the fluorescence of the community was measured each day. The chlorophyll-a content and ICPMS concentrations were sampled on the seventh day of the incubations during the exponential growth phase of the community, for test tubes which received the lowest and highest dust treatments. At the end of the experiment, on the sixteenth day, another set of samples was taken for ICPMS analysis and phytoplankton community composition.

4. Hazard index

The calculation of the hazard index was done with the same methodology as presented in Vos et al. [40]. This methodology is repeated here:

The US EPA health risk assessment model relies on the "maximum exposure" concentration of certain metals. This value is generally defined as the 95% Upper Concentration Limit (UCL) of the measured dataset. Due to the log-normal distribution of the metal concentration as confirmed by the Shapiro-Wilk test with an alpha value of 0.05, the "Land" method was used to calculate the 95% UCL using the EnvStats package in R.

To determine the impact of toxic metals in dust, the chemical daily intake of toxic metals (CDI) via inhalation through the mouth and nose (D_{inh}), ingestion (D_{ing}), and dermal absorption through skin contact (D_{dermal}) are calculated with the following formulas:

$$1. \quad CDI_{inh} = C * \frac{R_{inh} * F_{exp} * T_{exp}}{PEF * ABW * T_{avg}}$$

$$2. \quad CDI_{dermal} = C * \frac{SAF * A_{skin} * DAF * F_{exp} * T_{exp}}{ABW * T_{avg}} * 10^{-6}$$

$$3. \quad CDI_{ing} = C * \frac{R_{ing} * F_{exp} * T_{exp}}{ABW * T_{avg}} * 10^{-6}$$

Whereby C represents the elemental concentration (ppm), R_{inh} is the dust inhalation rate in $m^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$, F_{exp} is the exposure frequency, T_{exp} is the time of exposure, PEF is the particle emission factor in $m^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$, ABW is the average body weight (assumed 15 kg for children and 70 kg for adults, following US EPA [10], and T_{avg} is the average time of illness to develop ($T_{exp} \times 365$ days), SAF is the skin adherence factor in $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{ hr}^{-1}$, A_{skin} is the exposed skin area in cm^2 , DAF is the dermal absorption factor as a ratio, and R_{ing} the dust ingestion rate in mg day^{-1} . Details on these values can be found in Table 9.

Table 9. The values used to calculate the chemical daily intake (CDI) are described by formulas 1 to 3.

Value	Adults	Child	Source
R_{ing} : Dust ingestion rate	100 mg day ⁻¹	200 mg day ⁻¹	US EPA 1996; 2011
R_{inh} : Dust inhalation rate	20 m ³ day ⁻¹	7.6 m ³ day ⁻¹	van den Berg 1994; Zheng et al. 2010
F_{exp} : Exposure frequency	350 days year ⁻¹	350 days year ⁻¹	Ferreira-Baptista and De Miguel, 2005
T_{exp} : Time of exposure	24 years	6 years	USEPA 2001
PEF is the particle emission factor	1.36 * 10 ⁹ m ³ kg ⁻¹	1.36 * 10 ⁹ m ³ kg ⁻¹	USEPA 2001
ABW: average body weight	70 kg	15 kg	US EPA 1989
T_{avg} non-carc: average time of illness development	24 years * F_{exp}	6 years * F_{exp}	Zheng et al. 2010
T_{avg} carcinogenic: average time of illness development	25,550 days	25,550 days	US EPA 1996
SAF: skin adherence factor	0.7 mg cm ⁻² hr ⁻¹	0.07 mg cm ⁻² hr ⁻¹	USEPA 2001
A_{skin} : exposed skin area	5700 cm ⁻²	2800 cm ⁻²	USEPA 2001
DAF: dermal absorption factor	0.001	0.001	USEPA 2001

5. Soil samples

Figure 27: The results from the soil sampling activities, showing the Mn, Cr, Cd, and Pb in the different size classes.

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